

CODING MANUAL

Coding Manual: Nativism, Islamophobia and Islamism in the Age of Populism’, *ISLAM-OPHOB-ISM ERC Project*, Agreement No. 785934

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Values analysis identifies norms, principles to live by, guiding assumptions stated and/or clearly implied by narrators, in different positions around the issues of interest. Values are sometimes stated explicitly but also (often) expressed implicitly in the language style. Clues to these more implicit expressions include evaluative adjectives (“good,” “bad” “beautiful”...and other evaluative devices (“only” ...”) (notice that “value” is embedded in the term evaluative devices (formal theory for this dates back to Labov & Waletzky, 1967 and brought forward to contemporary narrative research); See also Daiute, in 2011; Daiute, Stern Leliutiu-Weinberger, 2003; Kreniske, 2012. Values revolve around topics, like education, professional roles, character qualities, BUT values are principles, norms, rules to live by, requiring a sentence to express not only topic/subject but also predicate – what is it about the topic that makes this a value?

Process:

1. Read the interview notes located at the end of the transcripts. Field researcher’s notes are very important to comprehend the context the conversation took place and have an idea about the interlocutor’s motivation to participate in the study.
2. Read the whole interview; read it again if needed. Becoming familiar with the narrative before coding is important for several reasons: 1) to appreciate and react to it personally; 2) to become familiar with the overall meaning; 3) coding will sometimes depend on references to/from other places in the narrative.
3. Code values by turn. Some field researchers took interview notes in a narrative form and some noted follow-up questions individually. Consider each 17 question groups as a whole and select all what has been transcribed under when coding. Subsequently, it is possible to select a specific paragraph or sentence(s) to specifically underline a value statement. Please note that not all turns express values; some might express more than one, although identifying a most relevant value is ideal. **The unit of analysis is the interview transcript, meaning that the expressed value carries the importance, not the place where the value is expressed.**
4. Identify the Level 1 category (See list below). This is usually a good place to start with identifying values. Each question is designed to focus on a topic related to the research.

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Nevertheless, some topics have overlapping areas of interest and thus, interconnecting values. To find the relevant category easily, locate the topic of the question in bold letters and find the related Level 1 category. In the meantime, it is okay to consider related value expressions located under other Levels than the topic of investigation.

5. Identify the Level 2 – Detailed code. If this is difficult, identify level 1 or 2 or both, move on and return to this response. Try to identify the major ideas indicated by the individual but try to limit the number of codes within the level 2 as much as possible. It is possible to find a lot of code being relevant to the turn. However, if two codes are clearly indicated, then there may be two codes applied. In addition, if the interlocutor is talking about one Level 1 category but expresses ideas related to another Level 1 category code both. For instance, if the interlocutor is talking about both social media and religion in one turn you can code both. However, try to distinguish, especially the codes related to the main concepts we use in this research (e.g., globalization, diversity, multiculturalism, etc.) as they will allow to make arguments about the actual use of specific values.

Tips when two or more values seem to apply to a turn: 1) select the value with the most specific fit. 2) Ask yourself “What is the Level 2 or necessity of having more than few Level 2 codes for this turn?”

6. Review all coding, and revise and re-categorize as appropriate. If you move on without checking the coding of an interview, return to it later.

Level 1:

Codes related to [Personal History](#);
Codes related to [Neighborhood](#);
Codes related to [Personal Mobility](#);
Codes related to [Diversity](#);
Codes related to [Religion](#);
Codes related to [Economics](#);
Codes related to [Country Politics](#);
Codes related to [Social Media](#);
Codes related to [Political Participation](#);
Codes related to [Globalisation](#);
Codes related to [EU Authorization](#);
Codes related to [Envisioning Future](#)

Level 2

Decision among the various values under each Level one category. It’s okay to use context, that is reading forward or back to determine specificity. Nevertheless, do not overdue reading in.

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Level 3

Decision among the various values under two categories: 1) Values spontaneously introduced and 2) Values prompted by the research question. Categorize the first when the values are introduced spontaneously, not necessarily answering a question, or when the interlocutor detailed their answer. The latter often involve direct response to the questions in the interview guide.

Values relevant to PERSONAL HISTORY

Can you please talk **about yourself**? We are more interested in learning about your place of birth, your occupation, your education, your parents’ educational and professional background, your marital status, and whether you have any children.

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

1. **PerHis_Mobility**: Acknowledging the mobility experiences throughout life is important. This might involve either personal mobility experiences as well as family members’ or friends’.

Example: *I am originally from a little town of Bourgogne, in the département [district] of Saône-et-Loire. I lived in different places in France. I was in Dijon for the high school, and then I obtained a Bac S. I wanted to live in a big city : therefore, I applied to universities in Lyon for studying.*

2. **PerHis_Family Problems**: Acknowledging the significance of family members’ influence on the narrator is important (in the form of support or obstacle).

Example: *They were divorced when I was still very young, this was very hard and difficult for me because they fought and argued a lot (“vechtscheiding”, literally, fighting divorce).*

3. **PerHis_Friendship Problems**: Acknowledging the friendship problems (e.g. being bullied, lacking friends, etc.) experienced in school or neighborhood is important.

Example: *At school, I did not keep up well in class, socially. I was tested and it showed that I am highly intelligent. But I was lagging behind in social development, you see that more often with highly intelligent children. Because of this I was bullied at school.*

4. **PerHis_Discrimination**: Recognizing experiences of discrimination, acknowledging feelings of insecurity around members of majority society or authority figures is important.

Example: *The teachers there said: That the children in Chorweiler are not so educated because their parents don't foster them and that the children in German families are fostered more. “I couldn't stand that any more” after two weeks. “I didn't feel comfortable there.”*

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5. **PerHis_Economic Issues and Activities:** Acknowledging financial issues and/or activities (e.g. having worked in many different jobs, employment, suspending or dropping out of school because of money related issues, etc.) in life is important.

Example: *Financially it wasn't easy. Actually, at that time I preferred to work instead of obtaining my university entry certificate by going to another school. I worked fulltime at McDonald's; my dad had connections there. But I didn't want to get old in a blue-collar job.*

6. **PerHis_Past Crime:** Acknowledging past criminal and unlawful behavior is important.

Example: *I went the wrong way and somewhat landed on the streets. I went less and less to school, found friends on the streets. I sank to a low level at the time I was between eleven and twelve years old. Among other bad things that I did, I sold drugs.*

7. **PerHis_Religious Development:** Acknowledging personal religious trajectory and practices is important.

Example: *When I was 17 I wanted to deepen my religious knowledge. I was motivated to do so because during that time ISIS came up, youngsters left for Syria and I was confronted with a lot of questions about terrorism and Islam. But, I never knew how to answer those questions. There was a lot going on in the public/ societal debate and I kept wondering why these youngsters left for Syria.*

8. **PerHis_Organization Membership:** Acknowledging membership of and commitment to an organization is important.

Example: *I've been a member of the SGP since I was eleven. And when I was seventeen I applied for the vacancy "international". I do all of this on a voluntary basis.*

Values Prompted by the Research Questions

9. **PerHis_Educational Experiences:** Recognizing the importance of educational experiences is important.

Example: *I did all my schooling in the same private school, in X, from my middle section in the kindergarten to the Terminale. Then I took the Y exam : I had a choice between two universities, and I chose Lyon, following the advice of my father, who studied there. In addition, I had family in Lyon : my grandparents, my uncle and my cousins live there. Besides, my grandfathers were living very close to my future campus. I then specialized in economics and finance, during my studies. I went to Germany twice : I was in my second year at A, and in my fourth year at B. Then I did a sandwich course in my fifth year at company C, to finish my master's degree. I*

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really enjoyed this experience. I’ve always had an interest in the military industry, from my second to third year of my bachelor’s degree.

10. **PerHis_Parents’ Background:** Acknowledging parents’ socio-economic, financial, ethnic, etc. background is important.

Example: *My grandmothers were Italian immigrants who came to D to work, and then settled in Lyon.*

11. **PerHis_Spouse or Partner:** Acknowledging the current marital status or partnership status is important. This involves highlighting the partner’s involvement in life decisions.

Example: *I have lived in Brussels after high school, this is where I met my future wife and where we lived together. We moved here a few years ago to be able to offer our children better education.*

[Go up to Level 1](#)

Values relevant to NEIGHBORHOOD:

Can you please tell me about where you currently live? We are more interested in learning about your thoughts and feelings on local neighbourhood. Have you always lived here since you were born? How do you find the **neighbourhood**? Is this a friendly neighbourhood? Do you socialize with other people here? Do you like living here? What do you like here the most, and the least for example?

Are there any people in your immediate neighbourhood who migrated here from elsewhere? Where are they from? Are you interacting with them? Do you visit them personally? Do you think they are **welcome in your neighbourhood**? Why do you think they are welcome, or not welcome?

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

1. **Neighborhood_Safety:** Living in a peaceful, green and/or safe neighborhood is important.

Example: *This is a quiet neighborhood. I like it, I like to live there.*

2. **Neighborhood_Old habitant:** Identifying the self as an old habitant (Witnessed the change in the neighborhood) is important.

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Example: *I live in a suburban neighborhood, near Lyon. Since my arrival in France, I have always been there. I have always lived there, first in my parents' home, now in my own home. In my opinion, this is a quiet neighborhood. It's nice to live there.*

3. **Neighborhood_Youth friendliness:** Judging the neighborhood by its youth friendliness (e.g. places to meet friends, sports events, cultural activities, availability of places to do sports, etc.) is important.

Example: *In this neighborhood there is no youth. Those who live here are losers. Most young people move away. This place has no future.*

4. **Neighborhood_Scarcity of resources:** Identifying the scarcity of neighborhood resources (e.g. public transportation, community center, clean streets etc.) is important.

Example: *I grew up in Capelle and I still live there, but I don't like it much. It has no soul, people 'don't like Capelle'. It is really a commuter city, everyone works in Rotterdam. it has only 60,000 inhabitants. We don't really have a historical center, it is all new constructed apartments and houses, built after the second world war.*

5. **Neighborhood_Keeping a low profile:** Acknowledging the hardship of keeping a low profile in a small place important.

Example: *For example, there are more gossips. Let's take an example : if you are from another place, and you take a drink in X or you take a drink in a bar at Y, people will react differently. Discussions will be different. They will begin to say « Who is this guy ? », « Where is he coming from ? », « What is he doing there ? », etc.*

6. **Neighborhood_Other's Orientation:** Excluding self when discussing other residents' political, cultural orientations is important.

Example: *In terms of values, I don't have much in common with them : look at the results of the latest mayoral elections. They voted Green to the max ! (.....) A certain naivety on security issues, I would say. A well-thought-out boboism that forbids seeing some problems. Many people of Lyon have the naivety to think that everyone is nice, everyone is benevolent ... That's a problem, I think.*

7. **Neighborhood_Problems caused by others:** Identifying the immediate problems stemmed from the current residents (e.g. blaming new residents, etc.) is important.

Example: *There are more and more people from sub-Saharan Africa or « French by the paper », because these people are only French by their identity card. They commit robberies, they commit thefts.*

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8. **Neighborhood_Similar background and ideology:** Living in a neighborhood where one can find people with similar background and ideology is important.

Example: *What I liked most was that I had a lot of friends there. I had a full social life. (...) However, for what I liked the least... It didn't come to me right away. I was immediately excited about it. But on campus and in the university, I found people very politicized, there was a latent ideology that we were taught, in my university, but I didn't feel it right away. An ideology that was cosmopolitan, leftist, even communist in many ways. I felt that there was a strong left-wing militancy, but without counterpart. And the people in front of you were overreacting : as soon as you expressed the slightest disagreement, you were called a fascist. I think that influenced the choice of my groups of friends.*

9. **Neighborhood_Recent Migrants:** Acknowledging the recent changes in migrant population in the neighborhood is important.

Example: *Today's migrants are the Romanians, the people from Eastern Europe. Them, in contrast, they have a big problem of integration within our society. They are too different ... The way they act, the way they speak ... For instance, they throw their trashes out ... That's impossible to live it ...*

10. **Neighborhood_Engage with others:** Trying to engage with other neighbors with different background than theirs is important.

Example: *Oh I forgot them : we have also many Asian families. People from Thailand, from Vietnam, or from Japan. I'm not sure. Frankly, we should recognize that they all look a little bit alike (Little laughs). In a nutshell, we are often all together. We invite each other to dinners. When we have some specific needs, we are gathering. And we organize some little events : for instance, on Sundays, we like barbecuing, grilling ...*

11. **Neighborhood_Integration vs. Assimilation:** Differentiating integration from assimilation, recognizing nuances in regards to accepting and welcoming people with diverse background is important.

Example: *You know integration is fine, but when they ban the headscarf it is because they prefer assimilation, not integration.*

12. **Neighborhood_Assimilating:** Assimilating to the rules and life of the country one moves in is important.

Example: *When we arrive in another country, we need to adapt to the practices, to the way of life of the country ... We should accept the customs of the country ...*

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Example2: *The question is to what extent these children are prepared to take up a place in our complex society without a good knowledge of Dutch. But of course they have their own community in the meantime.*

13. **Neighborhood_Friendly Exchanges:** Emphasizing friendly exchanges between residents of the neighborhood is important.

Example: *Yes, because I am very sociable by nature (Laughs). I have had neighbors at my house before. For tea, etc. The usual things. For example, I sometimes chat with my neighbor, who lives in the middle of our hallway. She was pregnant like me, and she gave birth before me. Obviously, that creates links ... I have a Turkish neighbor on the sixth floor, with whom I get on well. There is also the neighbor of the seventh, and that of the ninth ...*

14. **Neighborhood_Costs:** Cost of housing expenses, pricing of transportation are important.

Example: *I only sleep there. I live there because the rents there are cheap. I only pay 230 Euros for 32 square meters, including heat and electricity.*

15. **Neighborhood_Sympathy of Majority:** Receiving sympathy from majority group members is important.

Example: *We live in Schalkwijk, which is a neighborhood in Haarlem that is known for its great diversity, where mainly people with a Turkish, Moroccan or African background live. We do live in the whitest part of this neighborhood, there are only a few people with a migration background in our part, including ourselves. It is a nice neighborhood, quiet and mainly old people live there. What is less fun about this neighborhood is that my friends do not live here but in other neighborhoods. Not many people my age actually live here. I sometimes have a short chat in the street, especially with our neighbors, we have good contact with them. We also regularly help the neighbors, sometimes we bring food.*

Example2: *And my neighbors say that there was a garage owner here at a time, who only employed illegal immigrants. But maybe it was just rumors ... Are these rumors true or unfounded? I don't have proof of what people are saying, so I am suspicious towards these gossips. Generally speaking, I don't see any aggressiveness towards immigrants. Nobody throws stones at them. Nobody tells me « There are too many Blacks ».*

Values Prompted by the Research Questions

16. **Neighborhood_Past Neighborhood:** Comparing the current neighborhood to the previous place one has lived is important.

Example: *In my area in Nieuwpoort there are mainly other Flemish people living, and foreigners are only French people. Before in Antwerp it was much different, I lived there 9 years; there are*

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foreigners from everywhere, many Moroccans and Turkish lived in my area. I don't care where they are from, I judge people on their mentality.

[Go up to Level 1](#)

Values relevant to MOBILITY

Have you ever **stayed in any other city**, or any country before for long term, or a few months? Can you tell us where you stayed and what was your purpose? (For instance education, labour, EU projects, or other purposes).

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

1. **Mobility_Want to move back home**: Acknowledging the will to move to the country of origin is important. This value only concerns people with migrant origin.

Example: I wanted to go back to Turkey, and I stayed there between last July and the beginning of November or the end of October. I wanted to settle there, and my parents want to live there too.

2. **Mobility_Willing to move elsewhere**: Recognizing the interest in immigrating elsewhere is important.

Example: Otherwise I feel that I have nothing to prove to anybody. I sometimes think of moving to the middle east or north africa, but I need to work longer to be able to do that.

Values Prompted by the Research Questions

3. **Mobility_Visiting BackHome**: Visiting and staying at the country of origin/place of birth is important.

Example: Sometimes I'm coming back to the memleket, to visit the family... I stayed in Turkey a bit longer, but not for holidays. It was for an internship I was doing in Ankara. I loved this period.

4. **Mobility_EU**: Discovering and/or staying within the EU countries, including one's own country is important.

Example: In the past it was not self-evident to travel, now it is. I am also the first to go to university in my family and I have traveled through Europe, my grandfather never did, for example.

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5. **Mobility_Pilgrimage**: Going to places (e.g., Kabbah) with religious purpose is important.

Example: *I did the small pilgrimage several times.*

6. **Mobility_EU Programs**: Engaging in EU programs (e.g., Erasmus) and going to places through them is important.

Example: *As I said earlier, I stayed several months in Italy to do my Erasmus. I stayed there for seven months, between September and March. I would like to go back to Italy in July, but just for holidays, not to study.*

Example2: *As I told you, I have lived in Brittany, Paris, Valence ... It is in Valence that I lived the longest, however, before arriving in Lyon. Each time, I changed city to follow my family, simply. On the other hand, I have never lived abroad. I only stayed abroad for short periods, for holidays. And every time we went abroad, we stayed in Europe. We visited European countries, and that's all.*

7. **Mobility_Education**: Recognizing educational mobility is important.

Example: *Yes, I was in Turkey for three months last year. One month for holiday and two months for an internship in Ankara. The time during internship was the longest term I have been abroad in my life. It was a was a mandatory internship for my studies.*

8. **Mobility_Labor**: Mobility for employment is important.

Example: *I have lived a few months in Istanbul for work purposes, five years ago. I have many customers from Turkey, I do good business with them. As I said earlier, I never had any problem there, my business went very well. And I never encountered any problems while I was there.*

[Go up to Level 1](#)

Values relevant to DIVERSITY

Overall, when you think about your views on cultural, ethnic and religious diversity, or multiculturalism in general, do you think your world view is different from that of your family and friends? If so, in what ways? And does that have any affect on you?

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

1. **Diversity_In Betweenness**: Acknowledging the in betweenness of social identities and attitudes is important.

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Example: *You know, I'm from Nevşehir, and when you are from a region like this, you imagine that all Turks are like you, are like your family. And sometimes, I am a bit disturbed when I am walking there. The way people live, the way people behave, the way people speak. I had the same feeling in Ankara, during my internship : sometimes I felt a bit like a foreigner. I could not imagine Turks living like that, I could not imagine Turkey like that. This is so different from my family lifestyle, and from the lifestyle of my Turkish friends in France, by the way. In cities like Ankara or Istanbul, the mentalities are so different.*

2. **Diversity_Against Racism:** Evaluating and engaging in activities condemning racism (this implies nuanced theories such as critical race theory, post-colonial theory, global and local social movements against racism).

Related Code: Experiencing discrimination, Racial Inequality, Global Conflict

Example: *I think there could be done more. Because I think we definitely have a big problem with racism in Germany. Not only against Muslims, also against blacks.*

Example2: *In Germany right-wing settings in society are more perceptible in society. This influences Muslim people as well as the non-Muslim society. It [politics] should take more action against racism. Especially in the US. George Floyd. I am thankful that topics such as racism, unequal chances of opportunity are taken up more [in the public sphere in Germany] and that society is sensitized more regarding those topics.*

3. **Diversity_Challenge Mainstream:** Challenging mainstream viewpoints and conducts of politics is important (this sometimes involves critiquing the small community one belongs to).

Related Code: Illegal Action Yes

Example: *I perceive a clear lack of courage and political will. The political system is sick, just like the world... In the image of this worldist world. In my opinion, LREM embodies the sluggish block of the centre. LREM's proposals are lukewarm water.*

4. **Diversity_Immigrants Everywhere:** Emphasizing the ever increasing rates of immigrants and refugees is important.

Example: *There is also a problem linked to the spread of political Islam in France. There are many places where this phenomenon is visible, in big cities, and even in medium-sized towns. Immigration is everywhere, and you can see it through some signs. There is increasing insecurity, even in small towns. There is more and more delinquency ... There is a political Islam which is on display : you see women wearing veils everywhere in France, and more and more. Some communities are more and more conquerors, especially the Muslim community.*

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5. **Diversity_Support Likewise:** Supporting and/or tolerating the ethnic minorities based on their religious and political affiliation is important.

Related code: Similar background and ideology

Example: *I am quite in favor of intra-European immigration. But I'm talking about the real European peoples: from my viewpoint, the Roma are not part of it. They come from European countries, but they are not European. But intra-European immigration must be limited, even if I myself come from intra-European immigration. On the other hand, I am against extra-European immigration, whether it is linked to the right of asylum or motivated by economic reasons. The only limit I would see is student immigration, but only if it is temporary. I have African colleagues in my master's program, and if they go back to Africa after their studies, then their presence here does not bother me.*

6. **Diversity_Stereotypes:** Acknowledging the role of stereotypes in social polarization is important.

Related code: Media representations, experiencing discrimination

Example: *Whenever I don't fit into a stereotype, or into expectations people have they are surprised. A man told me 'I wouldn't have thought that [you are Muslim].' I often get into an argument because of my political views but less because of my religion.*

7. **Diversity_Be Good Example:** Becoming a positive example in the community or beyond it is important.

Example: *I want to give my children a good and Islamic upbringing. I want to teach them what it means to be a good Muslim so they can be a good example to others.*

8. **Diversity_Understanding Others:** Being empathetic towards people with differing world view is important (not necessarily agreeing but understanding where their thoughts are coming from).

Example: *For example, I think that immigration can be a good thing, but I understand the party opposed to it. I understand the conservatives, who want to keep the territory: I do not necessarily approve, but I understand them.*

9. **Diversity_Hate Crimes:** Acknowledging recent hate crimes against parts of the population is important.

Related code: Experiencing discrimination, media representations

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Example: *That creates the basis for dumb people society, the basis for burning cars, for threatening people or for attacking a Synagogue (right-wing attack in Halle). An assault to (?) people. For example, the NSU murders.*

10. **Diversity_State Responsibility**: Acknowledging the state's responsibility in accepting and accommodating immigrant population is important (only when the interlocutor is complaining).

Related codes: Border regulation, Free movement, Skeptical towards Refugees, Welfare System (including the sub-codes)

Example: *There is a real counter-society which is developing, and which doesn't want to live in the French way, and the state allows them to do so.*

11. **Diversity_Non Interference**: It is important not to interfere with others' choices, even if they provoke one.

Related codes: Opposite opinions, Fam v. Friends

Example: *Concerning my friendly environment, I make a clear distinction between my comrades and my friends. For instance, I have left-wing friends ... I have even a buddy who is an ex-antifa, but we talk quietly. I have also friends who are « right-thinking » Catholics. On the political field, we disagree, but we have other kinds of affinity. I lived very pretty things with them.*

12. **Diversity_Subordinated Youth**: It is important for young people to be heard in various sectors of society.

Related codes: Participatory democracy, Collab with Youth

Example: *A lot of Youth in this country does not feel accepted by Society. too many are dependents on health insurance. we need to activate youth much faster and they should educate themselves and motivate themselves to work.*

13. **Diversity_Experiencing Discrimination**: Emphasizing the experiences of discrimination is important.

Related codes: Problems at work or school, Religious freedom, Inequality (including the sub-codes)

Example: *Conversely, Congolese burn down the Gare de Lyon and attack firefighters, and now, « oddly » enough, the government is not being tough at all. LREM is an anti-French party, and this government is showering them with taxes and levies to finance immigration.*

14. **Diversity_Media Representation**: Acknowledging the importance of media representation of one's group identity, ideology or religion.

Related Code: Correct media

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Example: *Also media feeds this, media tolerate bad behaviour from foreigners and so they feed it. And they (foreigners) know it, because also Moroccans and Turkish watch TV and read newspapers. They know that their bad behaviour is being tolerated and excused. Media mentions racism too easily and too quickly, while they cannot prove that it is really about racism.*

15. **Diversity_Welcome Refugees**: Welcoming refugees is important.

Example: *Consequently, people may fear the arrival of migrants who have different behaviors and lifestyles from their own. But personally, I think human consideration must come first. It is a duty of humanity, and a duty as a French citizen too. We are the country of human rights, after all.*

16. **Diversity_Skeptical Towards Refugees**: Being skeptical of the reasons why and how people seek refuge is important.

Related code: State's responsibility

Example: *Not everybody should be accepted. There are psychos and there are people who integrate themselves. It should be kept an eye on who comes here.*

17. **Diversity_Refugees to go back**: Expecting government officials to properly document refugees so they can be sent back later and refugees to be willing to go back to their country is important.

Example: *Most Syrians who come here eventually want to return to their own country, which is nice.*

18. **Diversity_Economic burden**: Considering refugee and migration phenomena as an economic burden is important.

Example: *I think that immigration, and issues like that, should be solved only through international solutions. I don't believe in national solutions about immigration : I think that the only relevant level to solve this problem must be international... immigration can constitute an economic burden for a country which would try to solve it alone. That's why I'm in favor of international solutions, about these kinds of issues.*

Example: *Economic refugees are a different story, they cause a lot of nuisance in the Netherlands. Moreover, they also cause problems in their own country, if everyone leaves the country no one will be left to create wealth.*

19. **Diversity_Immigrants' Contribution**: Emphasizing the contribution immigrants make to society is important (this might involve economic as well as cultural contributions).

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Related codes: Welcoming refugees

Example: *If I would be the state I would look if people can contribute something to the country. That qualified people can immigrate.*

Values Prompted by the Research Questions

20. **Diversity_Shared Opinion**: Sharing common political opinions with family and friends (the first and strongest reaction will be considered as some express dilemmatic opinions between family members) is important.

Related code: Family Influence in Pols

Example: *Globally no, because we share the same ideas, generally. Of course, I believe in family influences, in the construction of your political ideas.*

21. **Diversity_Opposite Opinion**: Opposing the political opinions of family and friends (the first and strongest reaction will be taken into account as some express dilemmatic opinions between family members) is important.

Example: *Well, with respect to my family environment I have the feeling that they choose the easy way. With their stance: 'You have to help people, no matter how, and there will be a solution somehow.' They never see what is needed and what things would actually mean in the background.*

22. **Diversity_Fam vs. Friends**: Differentiating political views of family from friends' is important.

Example: *My parents have an opinion similar to mine : it is more homogeneous. As for my friends, it varies.*

[Go up to Level 1](#)

Values relevant to RELIGION

When we talk about diversity in general, religion becomes an important element. So, can we talk about the role of **religion** in your life? Does it play an important role in your everyday life and does it influence the way you relate to your family, friends, co-workers? Do you regularly visit any particular place of worship?

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

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1. **Religion_IMA**: Emphasizing religion as religious affiliation is important.

Example: *In France, people are of Judeo-Christian culture, even when they are atheists. This is my case : even if I have a certain spirituality, I am an atheist, but I was nevertheless raised with Judeo-Christian references*

2. **Religion_Soothing**: Acknowledging the soothing function of religion is important.

Example: *I went to a psychologist before. I was aggressive. But that wasn't of any help. After praying however, I always felt better.*

3. **Religion_Problems at work and school**: Acknowledging the hardships of practicing religion in workplace or in school is important.

Example: *I wanted to become a teacher. But it's not possible with the headscarf.*

4. **Religion_Sorry to be not practicing**: Emphasizing the regret for not practicing religion fully is important.

Example: *At the moment I cannot reconcile wearing a headscarf a 100 percent with my weaker self.*

5. **Religion_Refuse to sin**: Withdrawing from doing things the religion considers as sins is important.

Example: *Drinking alcohol is forbidden in my religion for example. So, I don't hang out with people who drink.*

6. **Religion_Parents etc role**: Identifying others' role (parents, friends, relatives) in religious affiliation is important.

Example: *Religion is a gift that I have received from my parents and I'm very thankful for that.*

7. **Religion_Self-interest**: Emphasizing self-interest in learning about and devoting self to religion is important.

Example: *I had a sense of the divine within me when I was little. My mother did not educate me religiously, but I had the idea of God in me.*

8. **Religion_Religious interpretation**: Important to accept that believer's interpretation is apart from that of the community.

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Example: *I have faith yes, but that does not mean that I attend church every Sunday. I don't believe in dogma's.*

9. **Religion_Same religions across places:** Acknowledging the variety in the ways people from different nations practice the same religion is important.

Example: *I had read Not Without My Daughter some years ago, and it told the story of a Western woman married to an Iranian man. Her husband takes her to Iran with their daughter, to spend a holiday. Then the husband finally said : "We stay in Iran." He's holding them hostage in his country, her and their daughter.*

10. **Religion_Sense of purpose:** Important to use religion to give one a purpose, a sense of belonging.

Example: *With my friends, we push each other up. We find and send each other references, studies related with Islamic issues. We work on ourselves, we try to stay quiet through studying.*

11. **Religion_Empowering:** Acknowledging the empowering function of religion is important.

Example: *My motivation [for forgiveness] is my faith. Because I believe that one has to forgive. Rage, disappointment and hatred weakens you. As long as you don't forgive, you always have a spiritual barrier.*

12. **Religion_Philosophy:** Acknowledging the philosophy behind religion is important.

Example: *Well, it harmonizes and mixes with human dimensions. You are nice to your opposite. You don't break hearts, you don't gossip, you are not unfair. These are principles that keep you away from certain deeds. Sometimes when certain emotions, certain thoughts come up you say, 'Drop it.' That's not the way the creator wants it.*

13. **Religion_No Forceful Faith:** Being critical about the people who force religion upon others is important (this sometimes involve identifying extremists).

Example: *I am atheist, but I respect any body's religious positions, I respect believers as long as they do not enforce their opinions and beliefs onto others.*

14. **Religion_Privatized religion:** Emphasizing the private aspects of religion is important.

Example: *My religion doesn't influence how I deal with others. I only act it [the religion] out within my own four walls.*

15. **Religion_Disinterest in religion:** Emphasizing disinterest in religion is important.

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Example: *No, not at all. I have nothing to do at all with religion.*

16. **Religion_Secularism**: Separation of state and religion is important.

Example: *School is a national and public service, so it must remain secular. And in my opinion, laïcité should also apply to the public space : I don't see why the veil should be accepted in public.*

Values Prompted by the Research Questions

17. **Religion_Practicing**: Acknowledging the religious practices (e.g., praying five times a day, going to church on Sundays, etc.) one engages in is important.

Example: *Yes of course, we can speak about it ... I'm a Muslim, a practicing Muslim. My wife is a practicing Muslim, and my parents too.*

- **Religion_Community ties**: Highlighting the importance of community ties in religious experiences. (this involves going to regular religious meetings, going to the same mosque, church, etc.)

Example: *I joined the Millî Görüş because I was participating to the mosque activities every time. Furthermore, I have realized that it is easier to reach the people as a member of an association than as a simple individual.*

[Go up to Level 1](#)

Values relevant to ECONOMICS

Have you noticed your family's **economic situation** changing drastically over the past few years? What do you think has caused that change?

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

1. **Economics_High living costs**: Identifying increase in living expenses is important.

Example: *The consequences of the crisis are tangible because prices are more expensive but otherwise things have been quite stable.*

2. **Economics _ Work for family income**: Working to increase family income is important.

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Example: *My family and me were not too much impacted, because we are well organized. So we were not impacted. Of course, we had more difficult periods : for instance, my father already experienced unemployment periods.*

3. **Economics_Currency exchange**: Identifying currency exchange rates between different countries is important. This frequently involves the exchange rate between the country of origin and the country of residence for self-identified Muslim youth.

Example: *The reason for the change is that the Euro is worth a lot more in Turkey. In Turkey the apartment salespeople benefit a lot from that. They like to sell to people who work in Germany.*

4. **Economics_High taxes**: Identifying raised taxes as the cause of change in personal economic situation, recognizing the tax increase is important.

Example: *In my opinion, the rise of taxes, or the rise of some prices like the oil's affected our economics, but without destabilizing it however. Indeed, the State is trying to cover its deficit, so it increases its taxes.*

Values Prompted by the Research Questions

5. **Economics_No Change or Slightly better**: Identifying no change or slightly better changes in personal economics overtime is important.

Example: *It has not really changed, no. My parents have been doing well with their own business, they have a large general food store.*

6. **Economics_No or low income**: Recognizing bad economic developments in personal as well as societal life is important. This might involve low level of income as well as the increasing unemployment rates, the decreasing in salaries etc.

Example: *Frankly, yes. I noticed a change. If I think about five years ago, we were living better.*

[Go up to Level 1](#)

Values relevant to COUNTRY POLITICS

While we assume the importance of politics in our everyday life, I should start by asking whether you are interested in **politics**? If so, what do you think about the political situation in this country today?

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What do you think about the responses of the government and the oppositional parties to the current socio-economic problems (such as deindustrialization, unemployment, inequality, financial crisis, refugee crisis)?

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

1. **Country politics_Policies against minority:** Acknowledging uneven policies and practices against people with different religious and ethnic background is important.

Example: *It is very difficult to deal with parties like Vlaams Belang, the fact that they are so popular and so. It is poisonous.*

2. **Country politics_Our Problems Our Job:** It is important to prioritize job related problems as opposed to cultural problems.

Related Code: Unemployment, Economic burden, Welfare chauvinism

Example: *Anyway, it's worrying, as a French, to hear the French media speaking about Erdoğan every time. Then, they say he's an Islamist, but it's probably related to Islamophobia. Let's look at our problems here, first!*

3. **Country politics_Strong supporter:** Being outspoken about political leader/ party one supports is important.

Example: *Democracy should go above all, now all voters for VB are not being heard, this is profoundly undemocratic.*

4. **Country politics_Correct media:** Recognizing the strong influence of media content has on political discourse is important. This involves acknowledging the importance of media in transferring correct news and information as well as people putting effort in finding true news and information.

Example: *I do not have the feeling that I live in a democracy, or that I live in a free country. Media is a great problem, they should strive to keep politics fair and transparent but they fail in their job.*

Values Prompted by the Research Questions

5. **Country politics_Strong interest here:** Having strong political opinions, being interested in politics is important.

Example: *Yes I consider myself as being interested in politics, both in Belgium and internationally.*

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6. **Country politics_Disinterested**: Emphasizing disinterest in political news, disengaging self from politics is important. This usually does not involve negative connotations as to how narrators found politics dishonest, malevolent, etc.

Example: *Frankly, I don't have a great interest towards politics, even if I have convictions, even if I have values.*

7. **Country politics_Discontent**: Emphasizing discontent with the current political parties/figures, recognizing political grievances is important.

Example: *Politicians are not aware of the realities and the impediments that people face. In my job, you see the other side and the distance between politicians's talk and reality.*

8. **Country politics_Positive current politics**: Emphasizing the political satisfaction with the current political governance is important. This only involves national politics.

Example: *The [government] did a lot during the Corona crisis. They helped a lot.*

[Go up to Level 1](#)

Values relevant to SOCIAL MEDIA

How are you being informed about what is going on in your country and in the world? Are you using **Social media platforms** such as Twitter, Facebook or Instagram? Some of these platforms or other sites such as forums, chat rooms, YouTube channels allow people to form networks and even friendships based on their interests. Do you feel connected to an online community based on your worldview?

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

1. **Social Media_Online debates**: Observing or participating in online debates is important.

Example: *I am using all these social media, but for different (and distinct) reasons. I have a Twitter account to follow society debates, whereas I go on YouTube when I want to inform myself, to be more cultivated.*

2. **Social Media_Politician accounts**: Following politicians' accounts is important.

Example: *That's why I prefer Facebook, to inform. For instance, I like the lives made by Aurélien Barrau. I follow him too. And I follow the speeches of the president and the prime minister.*

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3. **Social Media_Accountable users**: Holding people accountable for their social media posts is important.

Example: *I use everything. I follow the entire political spectrum from left to right. Stories always have two sides, and you have to keep realizing that. Moreover, otherwise you will very quickly end up in a bubble where only your own ideas are confirmed.*

4. **Social Media_Sharing**: Documenting and sharing news and opinion on social media is important.

Example: *On Facebook I only share political stuff, no longer and private pictures. It's fifty fifty how people react to that.*

5. **Social Media_Using professionally**: Using social media professionally is important (this involves business, political career, networking for an organization).

Example: *Yes. Facebook I mostly use professionally for politics.*

Values Prompted by the Research Questions

6. **Social Media_For news**: Following the news on social media is important.

Example: *Yes, I am using Twitter to follow the news.*

[Go up to Level 1](#)

Values relevant to POLITICAL PARTICIPATION

There could be many ways of participating in politics and influencing the policy-making processes. Do you think **voting** is an important way of influencing politics in this country? Have you ever voted? If yes, or no, why?

Have you ever joined **an organization** that deals with social, economic, political issues? If yes, what kind of group, or organization it was? What motivated you to join that?

What do you think about **street demonstrations**? Have you ever participated in street demonstrations? Why? If yes, have you done anything unconventional (e.g. painting graffiti on government buildings to express a political message or trying to stop the building of roads by chaining yourself to trees etc during the demonstrations)? Would you consider doing it? Do you think disobeying the law could be justified to pursue political objectives?

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

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1. **PolParticipation_Local politics:** Emphasizing the importance of local aspects in policy making, participating in local councils/politics are important.

Example: *We are registering people in the electoral lists. We want to see our potentiality of vote. We want to see how much we weigh.*

2. **Polparticipation_Country of origin politics:** Recognizing the value in following the politics of the country of origin is important.

Example: *Personally, I was imagining you will ask me questions about Turkish politics, about the Turkish political situation. I am kind of surprised that you did not ask questions about my personal views on Turkish politics.*

3. **PolParticipation_Other places’ pols:** Acknowledging the interrelations between different countries, shifting the focus and considering politics of different places is important. This involves either referrals to successful political conducts or places where the help is needed.

Example: *Everybody can tell you everything. ‘It’s not worth helping people in Yemen’. Well I think you have to start somewhere.*

Example2: *People do not really do any research. My opinion also differs because I want to help people far away in Africa for example, people who have the most urgent problems.*

4. **PolParticipation_Not trusting pols:** Recognizing the reservations about politicians’ conducts, being critical of and voicing mistrust towards them is important.

Example: *Politicians usually lie, look at Charles Michel. He raised fuel prices although he stated that he would not. He raised VAT although said he would not.*

5. **PolParticipation_Critical past:** Being critical of one’s previous political activity is important.

Example: *It is impossible to erase twelve years from your life. You can never say, that you forgot everything. Especially now [these days] it is more difficult to give up the ideology. That I gave up the ideology does not mean at all that I don’t have a memory.*

6. **PolParticipation_Family influence:** Identifying family as a source of influence with regards to political actions and interests is important.

Example: *Voting is very important and I always vote together with my parents, in both Belgium and Turkey. I think it is principally very important.*

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7. **PolParticipation_Freedom of expression**: Recognizing the merit of freedom of speech, questioning the limits of the right is important.

Example: *That’s a no go. It showed how far freedom of opinion can go. Freedom of expression goes very far, but also has limits.*

8. **PolParticipation_Collab with youth**: Acknowledging young people’s involvement in organizational processes, collaborating with them to build a community, a social capital is important.

Example: *Concretely, for example, I meet with some twenty youngsters, and we talk about topics which interest them ... Such as “What can I eat ?”, etc. Topics about day-to-day life, in a nutshell. It’s necessary, because we don’t want our youngsters go to the discotheques, we don’t want they get lost, etc.*

9. **PolParticipation_Police**: Emphasizing the role police forces play in organizing everyday life is important.

- **Police_Positive**: It is important to support and respect police.

Example: *When the police tell me to get up during a sit-in, not getting up is legitimate. But to throw a stone at a police officer or to a police car window is no longer legitimate. Only civil disobedience. Violence leads to division and strengthening the opposing party in comparison to civil disobedience.*

- **Police_Negative**: It is important to recognize negative experiences with police and the excessive power they have.

Example: *What I get is that the right-wing radical scene has infiltrated the police and the armed forces. Politicians turned a blind eye, concealed it. That’s alarming. It is dangerous, when these institutions are discolored. That attracts my attention*

Values Prompted by the Research Questions

10. **PolParticipation_Voting**: Voting in elections is important.

Example: *Voting is not only a right : this is a duty. We are forced to get involved in it.*

11. **PolParticipation_Voting does not work**: Acknowledging the little to no power voting has in election processes is important.

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Example: *Voting is important yes, and I do vote but my vote does not count, it is not valuable.*

12. **PolParticipation_Voluntary work**: Doing voluntary work is important.

Example: *I have always been very much interested in education and health care, at school I study to become a care giver.*

13. **PolParticipation_In political parties**: Recognizing the importance of being involved in political parties, emphasizing the personal experiences of political party engagement in the form of formal membership are important.

Example: *A long time ago, 2007-8, I once joined list LDD (Lijst DeDecker – this small party is right-wing and deep capitalist but only had a few MP’s and then disappeared from the national scene) and I was a candidate on their list for Sint Truiden.*

14. **PolParticipation_Membership to an organization**: Acknowledging the importance of membership to organizations (clubs, associations, etc.) is important.

- **Student club/council/parliament**

- Example: *We had such an association in X. It was called the Students’ Association [Association des Etudiants] : it was on campus, and there was a mosque behind the association’s premises, which was in fact just a prayer room.*

- **Sports club**

- Example: *I have also been a member of sports associations. I went swimming for ten years, I did a year of boxing at W. I also did a year of American football at X.*

- **Others**

15. **PolParticipation_Protests yes**: Participating in or acknowledging the value of street demonstrations is important.

Example: *I have to express my political interest somewhere. This is the only way, to give my opinion. “Since I can’t participate in the elections”.*

16. **PolParticipation_Protests useless**: Acknowledging the little to no power street demonstrations have in democratic processes is important. This often involves an emphasis on disturbances or questions regarding their efficiency.

Example: *I never participated in a demonstration. I was joining demos when I was a child, but it was to enjoy. But if I can speak frankly, I find it useless.*

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17. **PolParticipation_Yes protests but no participation**: Recognizing the merit of street demonstrations but not having had participated in one is important.

Example: *But I never went to a demonstration because there was no demonstration which I support a 100 percent.*

18. **PolParticipation_Illegal action yes**: Acting upon one's political thoughts despite the action being illegal is important.

Example: *Civil disobedience, yes. For example, like in the demonstrations against the limitation of the basic rights due to the Corona restrictions.*

19. **PolParticipation_Remind law**: Acknowledging the function of law or morals against illegal demonstrations is important.

Example: *Well, the duty to obey cannot be infinite. But I nevertheless support abiding the law. Disobeying sounds so martial. I think the police deserves respect. That law should be carried out with laws/legislation. But in extreme cases, when law is used to do injustice, then yes.*

[Go up to Level 1](#)

Values relevant to GLOBALISATION

Now I want to ask your take on the term, **globalization**. Some define it as the rise of international trade, economic outsourcing, the flow of people, interconnectedness, technology, etc. How do you define globalization? How do you see globalization influencing you, your family, this neighbourhood, this city, this country and the world these days?

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

1. **Globalisation_Economics**: Acknowledging the economic aspects of globalization is important.

Example: *In my opinion, globalization is when a country is opening up to the world market. I see it that way. It allows the growth of a country, through the opening of national markets to the international market.*

- **Consumerism**: Assessing the necessity of material consumption is important.

Example: *Through globalization people are being financially exploited, the big multinationals are taking over and societies are the victim of their power. They*

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make us believe we need a mobile phone that costs 1000 euro. But obviously this is not necessary. They are able to create a demand for certain products.

2. **Globalisation_Global Conflicts**: Acknowledging the global conflicts is important.

Example: If something happens in Mali it can influence people in Brazil or Japan. That if you start pulling on a thread, that it can have impacts which were unintended.

3. **Globalisation_Recent events**: Acknowledging the recent events (e.g., COVID19) concerning globalization is important.

Example: Global problems have national impacts and impact other countries. I am for adhering article 6 of the constitution, for adhering the Schengen and Dublin agreement. During COVID-19 we can see now that it is possible to keep the borders closed.

4. **Globalisation_Mobility**: Acknowledging the mobility of people, goods, information is important.

Example: I think globalization offers a lot more personal freedom, and every person has a right to this freedom to move and travel. Also refugees have the right to move and seek better places.

5. **Globalisation_Interest in others**: Being aware of the happenings in other places and reacting to them is important.

Example: When you are interested in something other than your own culture, I think it's great.

6. **Globalisation_Positive impacts**: Acknowledging the positive developments led by globalization is important.

Example: It has many positive and many negative sides. Being exposed to different ways of being and cultures is positive but the capitalist logics, the logics of money, behind globalization is problematic.

7. **Globalisation_Protect national identity**: Identifying the characteristics of majority society (e.g., language, cultural practices, economics, architecture), protecting national identity are important.

Example: By the way, French is a more ancient language than English ... We use too much English in France..... Of course, I'm not simplistic : I know there are positive aspects in globalization. You can communicate with other people, from other origins. You can develop links with everyone, from almost any part of the world. But I'm afraid that this process can wipe out a culture, a nationality.

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8. **Globalisation_Environmental issues:** Acknowledging environmental problems is important.

Example: *It is difficult to say if it is a positive or negative thing. If you look at pollution or global warming.*

[Go up to Level 1](#)

Values relevant to EU AUTHORIZATION

In light of what you have told us so far, let’s imagine that you are an EU official, is there anything you would want to change?

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

1. **EU_Move&Trade:** Recognizing issues related to mobility and trade are important.
 - **Border regulation:**
Example: *Concerning identity questions, the far-right is better. They propose to control the borders.*
 - **Fair trade:**
Example: *I am in favor of the European Common Market, because we share a common cultural consciousness.*
 - **Free movement:**
Example: *I would also keep up the freedom to travel which is something on the cultural level.*
 - **Free trade:**
Example: *I want a new EU where countries collaborate but without so much national intervention, I want to bring it back to how it all started, the EU, as a mainly economic collaboration.*
2. **EU_Unity:** Being in favor of supranational European system is important.

Example: *Personally, I would attempt to develop the good aspects of the European Union which already exist, such as free movement, or the absence of customs duties between member countries. Besides, this is a union which is pretty united, and in my opinion, that’s a positive thing.*

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3. **EU_ Individual decisions:** Acknowledging the hardship of making decisions as a union member is important. This often involves condemnations of the EU for obstructing countries' abilities to make policy decisions independently.

Example: *I think that the EU member states should have more freedom of choice. The decisions should be left to the countries as far as possible.*

4. **EU_ Currency:** Comparing the EURO to past currency rate is important.

Example: *Maybe the euro advantaged the German government, and yet ... I think it mainly benefitted big firms.*

5. **EU_ Migrant Flow:** Acknowledging the recent migrant/refugee policies and populations in the EU countries is important.

Example: *My position on this issue is both simple and complex. I am in favor of a total stop of immigration, and then of a remigration policy. I am in favor of a return of non-Europeans to their land of origin.*

6. **EU_ Participatory Democracy:** Acknowledging the importance of participatory democracy, recognizing the need for methods involving citizen's direct involvement in democratic processes (e.g., referendum, etc.) are important.

Example: *The voice of regular people is no longer heard in the media, they are not represented, they never get on tv. We lose touch with what regular people want.*

7. **EU_ Inequality:** Recognizing problems regarding inequality is important.

- **Distribution of wealth:**

Example: *The rich have to be taxed higher than the poor and we need another division of money that is more equal and fair.*

- **EU (State-level) Inequalities:**

Example: *I think I would change the PAC [Common Agricultural Policy], because it put on the same levels Bulgarian and Romanian peasant, whom I respect ... Because who are not the same than the French peasants. Because Bulgarian and Romanian peasants are forced to fall into debt for adapting their farms to European norms.*

- **Gender Inequality:**

Example: *Feminism is also playing an increasingly important role, we no longer accept that we are asked: how can you combine your job with taking care of your children? They don't ask that of a man, do they?*

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- **Global Structural Inequalities:**

Example: *We should compose a socio-economic plan for 100 years to retain the value of our sources but without exploiting other countries.*

- **Intersectional Inequalities:**

Example: *They don't do anything about the disadvantaged situation of Muslim women who try to find a job in comparison to (what they undertake) when other groups are affected (by inequality).*

- **Racial Inequalities:**

Example: *I want to make inclusivity the norm and to think of people as people, not just as citizens. We need more equity and not equality, the former gives you what you need and the latter gives everyone an equal share. I am in favour of the first.*

8. **EU_Religious freedom:** Acknowledging the need to take necessary measures for religions to be freely practiced and expressed is important.

Example: *Today, we are told that no religion should exist publicly in France. But religions raise human and universal questions. I think that religion should be more visible in the society and at school.*

9. **EU_Free-riding countries:** Emphasizing the economical – political contribution of one or few countries to the EU is important.

Example: *Instead, Germany should receive more power and a leadership role. Germany is for a fact the Net contributor of the EU. For the amount Germany is contributing the gain is – economically speaking – catastrophic. If you consider the number of seats Malta has in comparison to its population.*

10. **EU_Welfare system:** Acknowledging the significance of welfare system is important.

- **Against Welfare:**

Example: *Today votes are being bought. My own father has been receiving social security allowances his entire life. He never worked. He lived like that. Now he receives pension/ retirement allowance. This is not correct.*

- **Health Sector:**

Example: *Health costs are still incredibly high, this could also be reduced, or it would be much better if health care was cheaper.*

- **Housing & Bills:**

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Example: *The discrimination in the housing sector is also a consequence of their behaviour. Owners start to refuse them because of repeatedly bad experiences with them.*

- **Public education:**

Example: *We are way behind with schools. I don't know where the money goes but it doesn't flow into social facilities.*

- **Public transportation:**

Example: *The accessibility with public transportation could be better. Without a car – I have a car – it takes 15 minutes to get to the bus station. And with full shopping bags, that's not really nice.*

- **Salary & Financial support:**

Example: *Under the last government, the rate of child poverty has risen. This is something very telling and bad; Now many people are suffering because of the economic losses due to Corona.*

- **Unemployment:**

Example: *People who receive HartzIV should be gathered in a block [where they live together] and are provided with work. Where they can live.*

- **Welfare Chauvinism:**

Example: *VB has changed a lot over the years. It has become socio-economically more leftist, it is not against social housing for example, but it is against the current implementation of social housing, it wants social housing first of all for native citizens and not for migrants.*

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Values relevant to FUTURE

Having all these in mind, what do you think about your future?

Values Spontaneously Introduced by the Narrator

1. **Future_Optimistic:** Expecting and hoping for the best is important.

Example: *I think of the future very broadly. I'd like to travel a lot and would like to found a charity to help anyone in need. And of course I'd like to have a family of my own.*

2. **Future_Pessimistic:** Preparing self for the worse is important.

Example: *I am worried that a big war might happen again I am afraid of the global unrest in Europe and a growing distance between the peoples.*

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3. **Future_Mixed feelings:** It is important to consider both the good and bad possibilities in the future is important.

Example: *I hope that things will get better, that it will be easier to make ends meet.*

4. **Future_No expectations:** Expecting nothing, reflecting on indifference about future is important.

Example: *I don't have any idea on it. I am neither an optimist nor a pessimist, about my future.*

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